

Economic Governance in Ancient India: Revenue Collection and the State

Dr. Aasim Mir

Assistant Professor

Department of Management Studies

Baba Ghulam Shah Badshah University, Rajouri, Jammu and Kashmir, India

Email: aasimmir786@gmail.com, aasimmir@bgsbu.ac.in

Abstract: *The current research paper examines the concept of economic governance in ancient India presented by Kautilya's Arthashastra with special reference to revenue system and administrative machinery of the State. Kautilya's Arthashastra considers revenue not only a taxation source but as a well defined structure that connects all possible sources of the State for well managed governance. Through an organized network that include superintendents, collectors, spies and accountants, the King's administration was able to monitor income sources, prevents misappropriation of assets, ensure responsibility and accountability and maintain work order. The study also considers highlighting how Kautilya's Arthashastra integrates economic patterns with discipline and penalty and also presents to highlight the systematic model of governance where revenue collection was associated with welfare, social security, market regulation and supervision.*

Keywords: *Kautilya, Arthashastra, Revenue Collection, Economic Governance, State Administration, Taxation etc.*

INTRODUCTION: Kautilya's Arthashastra is one among the greatest works of the time that has been systematically written and organized to address all issues related to governance and administration in ancient India. It presents a deep understanding of devising a mechanism for offering strategic intent to an administration through development of strategic vision and mission that supports sustainable survival and expansion of administrative control and through an organized platform. The book also provides a procedural structure that is based on facts and evidences rather to work through a symbolic or a moral identity. It has also presented mechanism for integration and management of discipline, financial resources and administrative control. The framework presented by Kautilya's Arthashastra considers that collection of revenue is not only a matter of collecting wealth and framing taxation mechanism but it is a framework that holds the processes through which a King is effectively able to manage his people, army and other societal issues and aspects. Further it is a fundamental tool towards standing against his enemies and external influences. Arthashastra has been successful in efficiently linking agriculture with cattle, trade and other primary sources that are the major sources of food and livelihood. These include grains, cattle, minerals, forest resources, water etc. These are supported by a unified system called Varta agriculture in Arthashastra and all are the prime resources of the State. Further the text also considers economic stability for all and also points out that economic stability cannot be achieved in the absence of a well defined law and enforcement schedule. Furthermore Kautilya's Arthashastra has a special place due to its significant role in addressing economic vision of a State where a detailed administrative blueprint is devised and implemented that considers revenue generating sectors available such as mines, forests, land, roads, forts, markets etc which are supervised by a team of specialized officials who address each issue minutely and try to solves the problems within a stipulated time period considering all aspects of defined law. They also regulated all types of commercial behaviors and prevent loss to either of the

party. The administration under the control of King has been shown as a vast administrative and managerial system where each functional department controls everything spanning from stationed markets to moving trade within the country and over the borders. In order to prevent any type of manipulation by administrative heads or subordinates in official records or resources the Arthashastra has provided guidelines for integrating economic governance with surveillance system that comprises of people from all segments of society so that even a meager chance of fraud can be avoided. Therefore Kautilya's Arthashastra is not only based on a model of governance that only addresses taxation issues but a complete administrative system where wealth creation, revenue collection, fixing administrative accountability, regulation of market, promoting discipline and integration of all was the prime objective making Kautilya's Arthashastra an important text towards understanding how India was able to figure out the association between economy and the State.

LITERATURE REVIEW: Many scholars have studied Kautilya's Arthashastra in different and diverse perspectives and has considered the text as one of the important contribution by the author with respect to understanding the state as a strong political economy, a well established economic platform, effectively defined administration and managerial system and collection of revenue not only as a tax collection centre but has a unique plan towards sustainable growth and development. First and very important contribution was from R. Shamasastri (1915), who translated the Kautilya's Arthashastra into English language making it more assessable and understandable for authors from all over the world. His translation further enhanced the scope of study as authors from diverse segments started analyzing the texts with diverse perspectives. It further considered the study of text not only as a moral contribution but as a well structured system that led to expansion and growth of the state. Trautmann (1971), conducted a research study and found that the book has significantly stated the association of India's political system with administrative phenomenon and has also found an important role played by the text in understanding formation of great ancient India along with philosophical construction of parameters of kingship and authority. Kangle (1960-1965), studied Kautilya's Arthashastra through the mechanism of analyzing textual layers of the text and found that strong focus of the text towards administrative setup and institution based governance model and had a special focus on economic system of the State. Rangarajan (1992), brought attention of the text by presenting the work as a logical guidebook where revenue, regulation of market and welfare of the state work together as a unified system. Boesche (2002, 2003), considered that Kautilya's Arthashastra predicts some new dimensions associated with modern economy including refined supervision, governance based on intelligence and strategic association between power and wealth. The study also highlighted the role of ethical association between realistic control and public wellbeing. Thapar (2002) and Sharma (2007), studied the Arthashastra with perspectives like agriculture production, trade networks and expansion of State presenting how taxation, labour and extraction of resources led to shaping of political system. Kulke and Rothermund (2004), through their study were significantly able to align mechanism of revenue collection with different categories of the kingship like administrative divisions, official setups and several categories of revenue collection. Sen (1999) and Roy (2012), studied the functional and operational setup presented by Arthashastra. The book presented setup of different functional departments to regulate trade mechanism,

production system and maintaining public order as revenue was extracted from diversified sources like rural segments, forts, mining, forest reserves and trade and commercial routes. Singh (1993) and Boesche (2003), presented a new version of the text that focused on establishment of new instruments that support administrative verification for monitoring officials in several issues directly associated with the State affairs. Kautilya's Arthashastra is one of the best and refined models of economic governance where multiple aspects integrate to form a comprehensive administrative system.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To observe Arthashastra's view of economic governance as a foundation of state power.
2. To examine the revenue structure described in the Arthashastra and its major sources.
3. To analyze the administrative system of collectors, superintendents, and accountants used for managing revenue in Arthashastra.
4. To explore Arthashastra's mechanisms for controlling corruption and embezzlement in state revenue.
5. To recognize how surveillance support revenue collection and economic stability.

METHODOLOGY: The current research study has been conducted by using secondary data only. The data has been gathered by analyzing the text of book Arthashastra written by Kautilya. The data has been analyzed to address Arthashastra's view of economic governance, revenue structure described in the Arthashastra, administrative system of collectors, superintendents, and accountants used for managing revenue, Arthashastra's mechanisms for controlling corruption and embezzlement in state revenue and surveillance support towards revenue collection and economic stability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: The results from Kautilya's Arthashastra presented that the text effectively showed that economic governance in traditional India was laid in the form of a well structured mechanism and was categorized department wise in order to clearly define the functional segment linked with each category of tasks. The study presented that in ancient India collection of revenue, accounting standards, regulations with respect to trade and surveillance worked as an integrated system and laid operational foundation of the power State. Collector-General was the person responsible for collection of revenue from a wider and diversified segments classified as forts called durga in the text, mines named as khani in the text, buildings and gardens named setu in the text, groups of cattle called vraja in the text, forests named as vana in the text, traffic routes called vanikpatha and non-urban areas named as rashtra in the text. This indicated that income of the State was raised from multiple sectors making the collection of revenue more smooth and for maintaining its continuity. Representing the category of forts, Kautilya's Arthashastra listed several institutional revenue collection segments and points such as collecting fines from tolls, official seals, issuing passports to people, liquor stalls, measures and weights, goldsmith business from within the State, currency traders and lenders, warehousing of commodities, prostitution business, gambling business, craftsmen business, diversified business houses, taxes collection at gates etc that represented the urban life based on economic parameters and was completely regulated by the State departments. In case of rural segment the revenue collection included collection from production from crown

lands called sita in the text, government's share from production called nhaga in the text, taxes based on religious terms called bali in the text, money taxes named as kara in the text, other type of collection from merchants, rivers, ships and boats, towns, road-cess etc named as vartani. This reflected the mechanism adopted by rural administration through a combination of transport system, agriculture and livestock surplus and its merger into revenue structure of the State. The findings from the study also showed that the model presented by Kautilya on economic governance depends greatly on sustainable financial and accounting management system and expertise. The study also witnessed strong mechanism for assessing information with respect to generation of revenue from internal as well as external resources including system of identifying net income and gross income. This has made easy for identifying the several fixed and variable costs and findings the ways for reducing the costs over the coming period of time. Further it has made ways and courses of action towards analyzing new investment opportunities that could benefit corporations, State as well as the society in particular. The system was so managed that even funds were reserved and allocated in case of any emergency called contingency funds. The option was immediately exercised when any unpredicted event took place. Another key initiative adopted was recognizing all stages that led to loss in revenue including accessing all points where corruption arises. The text further presented mechanism for strict punishment for those involved in activities that led to loss of financial resources of the State. The sources that led to loss to the State funds have also been identified in the text as using state funds for self enjoyment, corruption of all type, un-notified barter of state goods etc. In addition to this Kautilya has been successful in establishing system for managing fiscal administration where village level accountants called Gopa and district level officers called Sthanika were responsible for managing detailed demographic profile of number of households and maintain economic registers pertaining to categorizing number of tax payers and non taxpayers. The system also maintained regularly people who are added as tax payers and those added as non tax payers. Further penalty and fine imposition system was activated for those who do not pay taxes on time. Designated system with respect to imports and exports was also implemented and reviewed from time to time. The review process includes increase and decrease of quota for items and changes made in taxation policy was also reviewed on regular time intervals. In the concluding lines it is finally acceptable that Kautilya's Arthashastra presents system of economic governance not only as an extractive system but also as a regulatory system. The appointed officers were responsible for monitoring demand, rise and fall in the level of prices, distribution of goods and services, avoiding benefits that harm local people, fixing trade and other sectoral taxes. The system also accounts for promoting foreign trade and maintaining a system that balances revenue collection, market stability and welfare of public.

CONCLUSION: Kautilya's Arthashastra has been found to be the most critical text that presented an organized framework towards maintaining a feasible administrative system. The text effectively presents an organized type of economic governance as well which was highly disciplined and framed as an institutional phenomenon and organizational system where permanence of the state is rooted through an organized system for collection of revenue, accounting standards and regular monitoring of individual and commercial activities and tasks. The text also presented that income of the state is not just for collecting taxes but is based on a

well managed structure drawn through the study of diverse dimensions. These diverse segments include collection from forts, rural provinces, mining, forest resources, herbs, livestock, trade routes etc thus showing the overall system is an integration of several diversified revenue channels. Kautilya's Arthashastra also had greater concerns towards maintaining discipline while maintaining state assets, financial projection for the future and untrodden events that may take place without invitation and training of officials for maintaining records accurately with respect to receipts, expenditure, working capital etc. In addition to this Arthashastra considers corruption and embezzlement of resources as a major threat to the state assets and presents mechanism for periodic inspections, evaluation from third party, punishment policy and legal enforcement through laws. The findings also depicted that economic governance could not be well implemented without proper surveillance and fixing accountabilities of individuals and teams involved in the system. Further the findings from the text also showed that Arthashastra also had a great focus on market regulation from the state officials towards managing prices, trading rules, international trade and distribution. This made ways towards enhanced nature of revenue and tax collection by the state. Kautilya's model aimed at an objective of not only increasing wealth and income but also to implement economic stability within the state. Finally the Kautilya's Arthashastra emerged as a complete framework in ancient political economy where wealth, administrative system, law and intellect collectively developed a system through which Indian state was able to manage power, security, development and growth.

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